

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS ELECTRONIC NEWSPAPER

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Abstract- Online newspapers, like printed newspapers, have legal restrictions regarding libel, privacy and copy right, also apply to online publications in most countries as in the UK. Also, the UK Data Protection Act applies to online newspapers and news pages. Up to 2014, the PCC ruled in the UK, but there was no clear distinction between authentic online newspapers and forums or blogs. In this paper made a study on consumer's preference, problems faced while reading e-newspaper, and their satisfaction level towards e-paper. For the purpose of the study 210 respondents were taken and to find the results demographic analysis, rank analysis, and weighted average score are the tools have been used. The study suggests that E-newspaper publishers may try to reduce the interruption of advertisement in e-newspaper and they must create awareness about the e- newspapers. The study concludes that online newspaper has its own importance and ever loyal customers because of its innovated strategies and psychological attachment of consumers to the e-newspapers.

Keywords: Newspaper, E-Newspaper, Online, Printed.

INTRODUCTION

An electronic newspaper is a self-contained, reusable, and refreshable version of a traditional newspaper that acquires and holds information electronically. Information to be displayed will be downloaded through a wireless Internet connection. Going online created more opportunities for newspapers, such as competing with broadcast journalism in presenting breaking news in a timely manner. The biggest advantage of e-papers has to be that they report news a lot faster than regular newspapers. Anything can be reported anywhere around the world. Online news is updated every single minute in real-time. Unlike when watching TV, or listening to the radio, online news service allow the user to choose which article they hear, watch or read.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **Tapu sheraba yatoma et al.,(2018)** examine ,“To read or not to read: Modeling online newspaper reading satisfaction and its impact on revisit intention and word of mouth ”.The study states the relationships between technological dimensions and reader satisfaction with online newspaper, expect for one. When the service is reliable, readers are more likely to be satisfied, and therefore to write or say positive things related to the website that provide the service.
- **Mr.A.Appuetal., (2019)**conducted a study on, ”Accessing the effectiveness of E- Newspaper among professionals with special reference to the daily newspapers in Chennai region: An empirical study”. This study states that choice between traditional newspaper and e-newspaper is mostly determined by the perceived ease of use. E-newspaper will always have loyal customers and it develops the reader's skills. Internet has become an important source of information and provides knowledge of different segment of society. Online communication system is changing rapidly day by day.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the preference of consumer towards reading e-newspaper.
- To know the factor influencing the consumer to read e-newspaper.
- To identify the problem faced by the respondents in reading e-newspaper.
- To examine the satisfactory level of the consumer towards reading e-newspaper.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Electronic Newspaper is a store house of knowledge. General Knowledge is an essential part of education. Electronic Newspaper is the best means for acquiring knowledge. The expectations of newspaper are vary from one customer to the other customer. It is very difficult to any business firm to except all the expectations of all customers but there are some common factors that are essential to fulfill. Life style and standard of living is changing day by day. It is need of the hour to work both members of the family. But it is difficult for the people to read newspaper during morning time. Hence the present study has been undertaken in “A study on consumer perception towards electronic newspaper”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This part explains the methodology used in this study. The methodology includes Research design, Sampling method, Sample size, Methods of data collection, Tools for analysis and Limitation of study.

Sampling method:

For the purpose of a study Convenient Sampling Method is adopted and it depends on primary data.

Sampling size:

Sample of 210 respondents were taken for the study, and the data were collected. Samples for the purpose of the study are selected systematically.

Methods of data collection:

The data collected for this study of two types' Primary data, and Secondary data.

Tools for analysis:

1. Simple percentage method.
2. Average score analysis.
3. Rank analysis.

ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION

TABLE 1:Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic factors	Respondents		
	Number	Percentage (%)	
Gender	Male	119	56.67
	Female	91	43.33
Age	Below20years	62	29.52
	21-30 years	100	47.62
	31-40 years	31	14.76
	Above 40 years	17	8.10
Marital status	Single	147	70
	Married	63	30

Area of residence	Rural	81	38.57
	Urban	99	47.14
	Semi Urban	30	14.29
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	20	9.52
	School level	37	17.62
	UG	115	54.76
	PG	38	18.10
Occupation	Student	103	49.05
	Private sector	46	21.90
	Public sector	23	10.95
	Business	29	13.81
	Other	9	4.29
Family Monthly Income	Less than Rs.25000	70	33.33
	Rs.25000-Rs.50000	78	37.14
	Rs.50000-Rs.75000	52	24.76
	AboveRs.75000	10	4.76
Types of family	Nuclear	149	70.95
	Joint family	61	29.05
Number of Members in the family	2	11	5.24
	3	49	23.33
	4	99	47.14
	5	27	12.86
	Above5	24	11.43

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is inferred that 56.67% of the respondents reading e-newspaper are male.47.62% of the respondents reading e-newspaper belong to the age group between 21-30 years. 70% of the respondents reading e-newspaper belong to the marital status of single category. 47.14% of the respondents reading e-newspaper have

urban area as their residence. 54.76% of the respondents reading e-newspaper have the educational qualification of under graduate level. 49.05% of the respondents reading e-newspaper are students. 37.14% of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the income level between Rs.25000 to Rs.50000. 70.95% of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the nuclear family. 47.14% of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the family having 4 members.

TABLE 2- Problem faced by the respondents while reading e-newspaper

S.No	Problems in e-newspaper	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage(%)
1	Advertisement	79	37.62
2	Server problem	77	36.67
3	Difficult to access previous information	40	19.05
4	Lack of device	14	6.67
Total		210	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table clearly shows that out of two hundred and ten respondents taken from the study, 37.62 percent of the respondents face problem in e-newspaper by advertisement displayed in between the news, 36.67 percent of the respondents facing server problem while reading e-newspaper, 19.05 percent of the respondent facing difficulty in accessing previous information while reading e-newspaper and 6.67 percent of the respondents face problem in reading e-newspaper because of lack of devices.

The study concluded that most (37.62%) of the respondents face problem in e-newspaper because of advertisement displayed in between the news.

Rank Analysis

Table No.3- Subscribed e-newspaper by the respondents

Name of the E-Newspaper	The Hindu	Indian Express	The Times of India	Dinamalar	Dinathanthi	Malaimalar	Other
Rank	I	V	II	III	IV	VI	VII

Source: Primary Data

The above table clearly shows that out of two hundred and ten respondents taken from the study, most of the students given first priority to The Hindu e-newspaper, second priority to The Times of India e-newspaper, and followed by Dinamalar, Dinathanthi, Indian e-newspaper, Malaimalar, and last priority given to other e-newspaper.

Average Score Analysis

TABLE 4- Satisfactory level of the respondents towards reading e-newspaper

S.No	Factors	Respondents						Total	Weighted Average Score
		Level	HS	S	N	DS	HD		
		Score	5	4	3	2	1		
1	Quick updates	Level	105	80	19	2	4	210	4.33
		Score	525	320	57	4	4	910	
2	News	Level	40	140	24	5	1	210	4.01
		Score	200	560	72	10	1	843	
3	Coverage of global news	Level	55	80	71	3	1	210	3.10
		Score	110	320	213	6	1	650	
4	Full description Of news	Level	44	100	41	23	2	210	3.77
		Score	220	400	123	46	2	791	
5	Cost newspaper	Level	53	87	45	10	15	210	3.73
		score	265	348	135	20	15	783	

Source: Primary Data

(Note: HS- Highly Satisfied, S- Satisfied, N- Neutral, DS- Dissatisfied and HDS-Highly Dissatisfied)

The above table shows that the satisfactory level of the respondents while using e-newspaper. The majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with quick updates in e-newspaper. This rank first according to the scores obtained.(scores=4.33)

The delivering of news is the next high level of satisfaction for the consumer while using e-newspaper. This obtained second high score.(scores=4.01).

Full description of news obtained third high score.(scores=3.77)

Costofe-newspaperisalsoanimportantfactorforsatisfactionlevelofconsumerwhileusinge-newspaper.Thisobtained fourth score.(score=3.73)

Coverageofglobalnewsisoneoftheimportantfactorsforsatisfactionlevelofconsumerwhileusinge-newspaper.This obtained a last score.(score=3.10)

The study concluded that the majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with quick updates. (score=4.33)

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION FINDINGS:

- Majority (56.67%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper are male.
- Most (47.62%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper belong to the age group between 21-30years.
- Majority (70%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper belong to the marital status of single category.
- Most (47.14%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper have urban area as their residence.
- Majority (54.76%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper have the educational qualification of under graduate level.
- Most (49.05%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper are students.
- Most (37.14%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the income level between Rs.25000 to Rs.50000
- Majority (70.95%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the nuclear family.
- Most (47.14%) of the respondents reading e-newspaper belongs to the family having 4 members.
- Most (37.62%) of the respondents face problem in e-newspaper because of advertisement.
- Most of the students given first priority to The Hindu e-newspaper

- Majority of the respondents indicate top priority to quick updates as highly satisfied among various other factors in e-newspaper.

SUGGESTIONS

- ✓ The E-newspaper publisher may try to reduce the interruption of advertisement in e-newspaper.
- ✓ E-newspaper publishers may give concentration for the coverage of global news.
- ✓ E-newspaper publishers have to create awareness among the public.

CONCLUSION:

The online e-newspaper is one of the most preferred media among people. Online news is updated every single minute in real time. In covid-19 lockdown started in China, India and other countries too. E-newspapers only easy search tool to know the day to day news in and around the world. Online newspaper has its own importance and ever loyal customers because of its innovated strategies and psychological attachment of consumers to the e-newspapers.

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